

A Molecular Dynamics Study of the Supercritical Evaporation Characteristics of Multicomponent Droplets with Different Polarity

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1. Introduction

Experiments and calculations show that the evaporation characteristics of fuel droplets change significantly in supercritical environments [1, 2]. Under supercritical conditions, the conventional clear vapor-liquid interface will be transformed into a transition region with changing density and component concentration, which is called the vapor-liquid mixing layer. The existing studies [3, 4] on the supercritical evaporation characteristics of droplets are mainly focused on non-polar long-chain hydrocarbon fuels, and there are few studies on the evaporation characteristics of droplets mixed with different polar fuels. In this paper, the supercritical evaporation characteristics of droplets mixed with different polar fuels (methanol-ammonia, methanol-n-heptane) are studied by the molecular dynamics (MD) method.

2. Research Method and Procedure

Fig.1. (a) Initial evaporation configuration of the methanol/ammonia droplet. (b) Initial evaporation configuration of the methanol/ n-heptane droplet.

The MD simulations were conducted using LAMMPS, a molecular dynamics software. In these simulations, the motion of molecules is calculated based on Newton's laws of motion. The interactions between molecules are determined by potential energy

functions. The initial configurations of evaporation are illustrated in Figure 1. The diameter of the droplet is 24 nm, and its initial temperature is 303 K. The spherical evaporation region has a diameter of 78.9 nm, and the thermostat region outside this region is employed to maintain a constant ambient temperature. In both cases, the ambient temperature is set to 1200 K, and the pressure is 14 MPa, surpassing the critical point of the fuel discussed in this paper. The ambient gas used is nitrogen. Considering the density of different fuels and their mutual solubility, the fuel percentage in the droplet is reasonably adjusted, and the relevant information is presented in Table 1. The simulations were performed using the micro-canonical ensemble (NVE), and the equations of motion were solved using the Velocity-Verlet algorithm. The SHAKE algorithm was utilized to keep the bonds and angles in methanol molecules rigid.

Table. 1. Information about droplet composition

Case		Mass fraction	Number
1	Methanol	63.02%	51511
	Ammonia	36.98%	56895
2	Methanol	56.57%	52883
	n-Heptane	43.43%	12994

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Droplet size variation

The squared droplet diameter d^2 was normalized by dividing the squared initial droplet diameter d_0^2 and time was also divided by d_0^2 . In the supercritical environment, the droplet evaporation reached a relatively stable stage after a period of heating, and the square of the diameter decreased approximately linearly with time, as shown in Figure.2 (a). Additionally, the thickness of the vapor-liquid mixing

layer continuously increased over time. In the late evaporation stage, the layer thickness for the methanol-ammonia droplet exhibited fluctuations around 4.5 nm. Conversely, the thickness of the layer for the methanol-n-heptane droplet showed abnormal growth before the end of evaporation, as shown in Figure 2 (b).

Fig.2. (a) Dimensionless squared diameter variation. (b) Variation of vapor-liquid mixing layer thickness.

3.2 Droplet component variation

As shown in Figure. 3 and 4, the supercritical evaporation of the methanol-ammonia droplet showed the characteristic of "stepwise evaporation", in which ammonia molecules evaporated predominantly, and the molar fraction of ammonia molecules decreased linearly and rapidly. The supercritical evaporation of methanol-n-heptane droplet showed the characteristic of "simultaneous evaporation", the molar fraction of methanol and n-heptane decreased simultaneously with time and changed little, and both of them dominated the whole evaporation process together. The molar fraction of nitrogen in both droplets first increased linearly with evaporation, but then increased rapidly after a certain moment.

Fig.3. Number of fuel molecules left in the (a) methanol/ammonia droplet and (b) methanol/n-Heptane droplet.

Fig.4. (a) Molar fraction of fuel molecules in the droplet. (b) Molar fraction of nitrogen in the droplet.

3.3 Hydrogen bonds variation

The number of hydrogen bonds in the vapor-liquid mixing layer was counted using VMD software, as shown in Figure.5. The number of hydrogen bonds within the layer of methanol-ammonia droplet decreased linearly with time, and the number decreased

by 90% from $t = 0.2$ ns to 1.2 ns. The number of hydrogen bonds within the layer of methanol-n-heptane droplet did not change much until 0.4 ns and then decreased linearly.

Fig.5. Number of hydrogen bonds in the vapor-liquid mixing layer.

4. Conclusion

This paper focused on investigating the supercritical evaporation characteristics of polar-polar, polar-nonpolar fuel mixture droplets (methanol-ammonia, methanol-n-heptane) by molecular dynamics. The important findings were shown below:

1. In the supercritical environment of this paper, the vapor-liquid mixing layer thickness of methanol-n-heptane droplets exhibited an abnormal increase during the late stage of evaporation.

2. The evaporation of methanol-ammonia droplets showed a "stepwise evaporation" characteristic, with ammonia molecules evaporating rapidly and preferentially. The evaporation of methanol-n-heptane droplet showed a "simultaneous evaporation" characteristic, with both components jointly dominating the evaporation process.

3. The number of hydrogen bonds in the vapor-liquid mixing layer was counted, and it was found that the number of hydrogen bonds decreased linearly with time for most of the evaporation time.

Acknowledgments

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5. Reference

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